

Effects of Biochar and Silicate Application on Soil Enzyme Activities under Nighttime Warming in Paddy Soil

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Climate warming has one of important characteristics that the temperature increase at night is greater than that during the day. Many reports have been available regarding the effects of nighttime warming, silicate or biochar application on the growth, physiology and yield in rice, but it is unclear regarding the effects of the three factors on soil enzyme activities in paddy fields. A field simulation experiment was carried out to investigate the effects of biochar and silicate supply on soil enzyme activities in rice soil under nighttime warming. The orthogonal experimental design with three-factor and three-level was adopted in the experiment. The nighttime warming was treated by covering the rice canopy with aluminum foil reflective film at night (19:00~6:00). The nighttime warming was set at three levels, ambient temperature control (W0), covering rice canopy with 5mm aluminum foil film (W1), and with 11 mm aluminum foil film (W2); biochar supply was designed with 3 levels, i.e., control (B0), 7.5 t·hm⁻² biochar (B1) and 17.5 t·hm⁻² (B2); silicate application had three levels, i.e., control (Si0), steel slag powder (Si1, 200 kg·hm⁻²), and ore powder (Si2, 200 kg·hm⁻²). Root bag method was used to separate rhizospheric soil from non-rhizospheric soil. The soil samples were collected at rice main growth periods (elongation, booting, flowering and filling) to determine the activities of urease, invertase, cellulase and protease in the soil. The results showed that, the activities of urease, invertase and cellulase in non-rhizospheric soil increased under nighttime warming with 5 mm reflective film (W1). Soil invertase and protease activities increased in the treatment without biochar application (B0), while urease and cellulase activities enhanced in the treatment with biochar application (B1 and B2). Silicate application increased the activities of soil enzymes mentioned above. This study suggests the treatment with W2B1Si0 is the optimal combination. Soil enzyme activities were inhibited in the treatment with W2B1Si0, implying that the

decomposition of organic carbon and nitrogen in paddy soil will be likely decreased with applying biochar without silicate supply under climate warming.

Keywords: NIGHTTIME WARMING, BIOCHAR, SILICATE, RICE, SOIL ENZYME ACTIVITY

Introduction

Climate warming is one of the main features of climate change. According to the sixth Assessment Report of IPCC, the global average surface temperature has risen by about 1°C since 1850, and the temperature rise is expected to reach or exceed 1.5°C in the next 20 years (IPCC, 2021). The climate warming is manifested by the asymmetrical warming of the day and night, that is, the warming of the night is greater than that of the day. Rice is one of the main grain crops in China. Tiller number, plant height, leaf area index and chlorophyll (SPAD) value of rice were significantly decreased by nighttime warming (Zhang et al., 2017; Li et al., 2019; Shah et al., 2016). Climate warming also reduced grain number per spike, seed setting rate and 1000-grain weight of rice, thus affecting dry matter accumulation and yield (Yang et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2013). Therefore, many studies have been available on the effects of temperature increase on plant growth, dry matter accumulation and yield of rice shoot, but less attention has been paid to the effects of temperature increase on soil biological processes and characteristics (such as soil enzyme activity) of rice shoot.

Soil enzymes mainly come from plant root exudates and microbial activity products, and participate in the process of material cycle and energy flow in soil (Liu et al., 2017). Temperature is an important environmental factor affecting soil enzyme activity. Previous studies indicated that, soil enzyme activity in wheat field was significantly enhanced under simulated warming conditions (Gao et al., 2019), and significant exponential relationship was observed between temperature and soil enzyme activity (Tang et al., 2021). The increase of temperature promoted soil respiration and enzyme activity, promoted soil microbial activity and metabolism, enhance soil nutrient availability, and promote soil material circulation and energy conversion.

Biochar is rich in organic carbon and a beneficial soil conditioner (Pazferreiro et al., 2015). Application of biochar significantly reduced soil bulk density, improve soil structure and increase soil water content. Application of biochar had significant impacts on soil nitrogen and phosphorus related enzyme activities (Rillig et al., 2011; Pazferreiro et al., 2014), and limited enzymatic reactions by adsorbing enzyme molecules (Lehmann et al., 2009). Application of biochar significantly increased soil catalase activity, but had no significant effect on sucrase activity (Chen et al., 2014). Biochar combined with nitrogen fertilizer significantly increased soil sucrase activity in paddy fields (Qu, 2012).

Rice is a typical silica-loving crop, and the silicon content in spike is about 10%~15%, much higher than NPK. Silicate supply could activate and promote soil enzyme activity (Lan et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2018), and significantly improve soil urease, invertase, catalase and other enzyme activities (Xu et al., 2008). The effect of silicate application on soil enzyme activity likely depended on the improvement of soil structure, and expansion of soil microbial growth space (He et al., 2019).

The purposes of this study were to investigate the effects of biochar and silicate application on soil enzyme activities in paddy fields under field conditions, and to further elucidate the mechanism of soil carbon and nitrogen conversion and emissions of greenhouse gases in paddy fields under climate change.

Materials and methods

Experimental site

The field simulation experiment was conducted from June 2019 to October 2019 at the Agrometeorological Experimental Station, Nanjing University of Information Science and Technology (32.0° N, 118.8° E). The station is located in the northern subtropical humid climate zone, with the same season of rain and heat. The average annual temperature is 15.6 °C, and the average annual precipitation is more than 1000 mm. The test soil was a hydromorphic paddy soil with loam clay texture. The soil contained 19.4 g·kg⁻¹ of total organic carbon, 1.45 g·kg⁻¹ of total nitrogen, 95 mg·kg⁻¹ of available Si, 261 g·kg⁻¹ of clay content (<1 µm), and 6.2 of pH value (soil : water ratio 1:1). The tested biochar was rice husk biochar with carbon content of 50%, which was provided by Tianjin Yader Biomass Technology Co., LTD. The silicate fertilizer was steel slag powder and ore powder. The basic physical and chemical properties of biochar and silicate fertilization referred to (Xing et al., 2021).

Experimental Design

The orthogonal experimental design with three factors and three levels was adopted in this experiment. The nighttime warming was set at 3 levels, i.e. control (W0), covering canopy with 5 mm aluminium foil reflective film (W1) and covering canopy with 11 mm aluminium foil reflective film (W2). Biochar was applied at 3 levels, i.e. control (B0), incorporating 7.5 t/ha biochar (B1) and 17.5 t/ha biochar (B2). Silicate fertilizer was supplied with no silicate (Si0), 200 kg/ha of steel slag powder (Si1) and 200 kg/ha of ore powder (Si2). Before transplanting, biochar and silicate fertilizer were evenly ploughed into the soil, based on the experimental treatment. In addition, high-concentration compound fertilizer (15–15–15) was basally applied to each plot at 200 kg/ha.

The tested rice cultivar was *Oryza sativa* L. cv Nanjing 5055. Rice seeds were sterilized with 10% H₂O₂ solution (v/v) for 5 min, washed with deionized water, and sowed into seeding bed on May 10, 2019. Rice seedlings were transplanted into paddy field on June 14, 2019. The rice canopy was covered with the reflective film at night (19:00–6:00) to simulate nighttime warming. The aluminium foil reflective film was placed on the top of adjustable frames (2×2×2 m) made of stainless steel pipe. The height of the reflective film was adjusted according to rice growth process to maintain a distance of 30 cm above rice canopy. In order to avoid the adverse effects of covering the reflective film, the canopy was not covered in rainy and windy weather (wind speed > 10 m·s⁻¹) at night. The plot size is 2×2 = 4 m². Except from the field drying period (July 28 to August 12), the water layer was kept at 5 cm by irrigation in the paddy field.

The root bag method was used to distinguish rice rhizospheric soil from non-rhizospheric soil (Steen, 1991; Cai et al., 2003). Rice seedlings uniform in size were selected to transplant into the root bags. One seedling was transplanted into each root bag. At the main growth stages (Elongation, booting, flowering, filling), one root

bag with rice plant was collect for rhizospheric soil.sample At the same time, the soil near the root bag was taken to obtain non-rhizospheric soil sample. The collected soil samples were put into plastic ziplocks and immediately brought back to the laboratory. Root residue, stones and other impurities were picked out, and then the soil samples were dried naturally, ground and sieved, and stored in plastic ziplocks for test.

Determination of soil enzyme activity

Soil urease activity was determined by indophenol colorimetry (Qiu et al., 2004). Soil invertase activity was measured by colorimetric method. Soil cellulase activity was analyzed by anthrone colorimetry. Soil protease activity was determined by ninhydrin colorimetry (Cai et al., 2005).

Data processing and analysis

Data processing and chart drawing were performed with the software of Microsoft Excel and Origin Pro. Statistical analysis was processed for analysis of variance and range analysis with SPSS software.

Results

Effects of different treatments on urease activity in paddy soil

As shown in Figure 1, with the change of rice growth stage, the urease activity in rhizospheric soil increased first and then decreased. The urease activity was higher at booting stage, but weaker at flowering stage. Except for W1B2Si0, W2B0Si2 and W1B1Si2, the urease activity in rhizospheric soil was the lowest at flowering stage. The urease activity in rhizospheric soil was highest at jointing and booting stages. The urease activity in non-rhizospheric soil showed a slight change in the overall range, which was stable at first and then decreased. Except for W0B1Si1 and W1B0Si1, the urease activity of other treatments in non-rhizospheric soil was the lowest at the filling stage. In rhizospheric soil, the mean value of W0B2Si2 treatment was the highest, and that of W2B1Si0 treatment was the lowest. In the non-rhizospheric soil, the mean value of W1B2Si0 treatment is the highest, and the mean value of W0B0Si0 treatment is the lowest.

The results of range analysis showed (Figure 2) that, for rhizospheric soil, the effects of the three factors were in the order of biochar > nighttime warming > silicate fertilization. W1B2Si1 treatment had the highest activity of soil urease, while W2B0Si0 treatment had the lowest activity, that is, covering 5mm aluminum foil film at night, applying 17.5t/ha biochar and steel slag powder promoted soil urease activity. At night, urease activity in rhizospheric soil was inhibited by covering 11 mm aluminum foil film and not applying biochar or silicate fertilizer. For non-rhizospheric soil, the influence degree of the three factors is nighttime warming > biochar > silicate fertilization. W1B2Si1 treatment has the highest urease activity in non-rhizospheric soil , while W0B0Si0 treatment has the lowest activity, that is, covering 5mm aluminum foil film at night, applying 17.5T /ha biochar and steel slag powder promoted the urease activity in non-rhizospheric soil . However, the urease activity in non-rhizospheric soil was inhibited without increasing temperature, applying biochar and silicate fertilization.

The results of variance analysis showed (Table 1) that, in rhizospheric soil, the effects of nighttime warming and biochar on soil urease activity reached significant level ($P < 0.05$), while silicate fertilization had no significant effect. In the non-rhizospheric soil, the warming had significant effect on urease activity at jointing

and flowering stages in rice ($P < 0.01$), while biochar and silicate fertilization had no significant effect on urease activity at key growth stages.

Effects of different treatments on cellulase activity in paddy soil

As shown in Figure 3, cellulase activity in rhizospheric soil decreased at first and then increased with the change of rice growth stage. The activity of cellulase was higher at flowering and filling stage, but weaker at booting stage and showed minimum value. The cellulase activity in non-rhizospheric soil under different treatments decreased first and then increased. The cellulase activity was low and reached the minimum value at jointing stage, increased significantly at booting stage, decreased again at flowering stage, and finally increased slowly at filling stage. In rhizospheric soil, the mean value of W2B2Si1 treatment was the highest, while that of W1B2Si0 treatment was the lowest. In the non-rhizospheric soil, the mean value of W1B1Si2 treatment was the highest and that of W0B0Si0 treatment was the lowest.

Range analysis showed (Fig. 4) that, for rhizospheric soil, the influence degree of the three factors was as follows: nighttime warming > biochar > silicate fertilization. The cellulase activity in rhizospheric soil under W2B1Si2 treatment was the highest, while that of W1B0Si0 treatment was the lowest, that is, 11 mm warming film was covered at night. The application of 7.5t/ha biochar and mineral powder promoted the cellulase activity in rhizospheric soil, while the treatment with covering 5 mm warming film at night, and no biochar and silicate fertilization inhibited the cellulase activity in rhizospheric soil. For non-rhizospheric soil, the influence degree of the three factors was silicate fertilization > nighttime warming > biochar. The cellulase activity in W1B1Si1 treatment was the highest, and that in W0B0Si0 treatment was the lowest, that is, covering 5mm warming film at night, applying 7.5t/ha biochar and steel slag powder promoted the cellulase activity in non-rhizospheric soil. The cellulase activity in non-rhizospheric soil was inhibited without biochar or silicate fertilization.

Variance analysis showed (Table 2) that nighttime warming, biochar and silicate fertilization had no significant effect on cellulase activity in rhizospheric soil. In non-rhizospheric soil, the effect of silicate fertilization on cellulase activity at rice at elongation stage was extremely significant ($P < 0.01$), while nighttime warming and biochar had no significant effect on cellulase activity.

Effects of different treatments on invertase activity in paddy soil

As shown in Figure 5, the invertase activity in rhizospheric soil increased firstly and then decreased with the change of rice growth stages. The activity of invertase in rhizospheric soil was higher at booting and anthesis stage, but weaker at jointing stage. The invertase activity in non-rhizospheric soil under different treatments showed a general trend of increasing, decreasing and increasing, and the activity increased at booting stage, then decreased at flowering stage, and finally increased at filling stage. In rhizospheric soil, the mean values of W1B1Si2 treatment were the highest, and W2B1Si1 treatment had the lowest. In non-rhizospheric soil, the mean value of W1B0Si1 treatment is the highest, and that of W2B1Si0 treatment is the lowest.

Range analysis showed (Fig. 6) that, for rhizospheric soil, the influence degree of the three factors was nighttime warming > biochar > silicate fertilization. The activity of invertase in rhizospheric soil was the highest

in W1B0Si1 treatment, and the activity of invertase in rhizospheric soil was the lowest in W2B2Si0 treatment. The activity of rhizospheric soil invertase was inhibited by 11 mm film and 17.5t/ha biochar application at night. For non-rhizospheric soil, the effects of the three factors were as follows: biochar > nighttime warming > silicate fertilization. The activity of non-rhizospheric soil urease was the highest in W1B0Si2 treatment, and the activity of non-rhizospheric soil urease was the lowest in W2B2Si0 treatment, that is, the non-rhizospheric soil urease activity was promoted by covering 5mm warming film at night, not applying biochar and applying mineral powder. Non-rhizospheric soil invertase activity was inhibited by covering 11mm warming film, applying 17.5t/ha biochar and no application of silicate fertilization at night.

Variance analysis showed (Table 3) that, nighttime warming and biochar had significant effects on invertase activity in rhizospheric soil ($P<0.01$), and silicate fertilization had significant effects on invertase activity in rhizospheric soil ($P<0.05$). In non-rhizospheric soil, the three factors had no significant effect on invertase activity.

Effects of different treatments on protease activity in paddy soil

As shown in Fig. 7, the rhizospheric soil protease activity changed slightly with the change of rice growth stages, showing no obvious trend of increase or decrease. The protease activity in non-rhizospheric soil under different treatments showed a general trend of increasing, decreasing and increasing. The protease activity at booting stage was significantly higher than that at other growth stages. In rhizospheric soil, the mean value of W0B0Si0 treatment was the highest, while that of W2B2Si1 treatment was the lowest. In non-rhizospheric soil, the mean value of W1B0Si1 treatment is the highest, and that of W1B2Si0 treatment is the lowest.

Range analysis showed (Fig 8) that for rhizospheric soil, the influence degree of the three factors was in the order of biochar > nighttime warming > silicate fertilization. W0B0Si1 treatment had the highest activity of rhizospheric soil protease, while W2B2Si0 treatment had the lowest activity, that is, steel slag powder was applied without warming or biochar addition but promoted the activity of rhizospheric soil protease. The activity of rhizospheric soil protease was inhibited by covering 11 mm warming film, applying 17.5 t/ha biochar and no silicate application at night. For non-rhizospheric soil, the effects of the three factors were as follows: biochar > silicate fertilization > nighttime warming. The protease activity in non-rhizospheric soil treated by W0B0Si2 was the highest, and that of W2B2Si1 was the lowest, that is, no warming, no biochar application, but mineral powder application promoted the activity of protease in non-rhizospheric soil. Non-rhizospheric soil protease activity was inhibited by covering 11 mm warming film, applying 17.5 t/ha biochar and steel slag powder at night.

Variance analysis showed (Table 4) that, in rhizospheric soil, nighttime warming and silicate fertilization had no significant effect on protease activity, while biochar had a significant effect on protease activity ($P<0.05$), which reached significant level at booting stage and filling stage ($P<0.01$). In non-rhizospheric soil, nighttime warming and silicate fertilization had no significant effect on protease activity, but biochar had significant effect on protease activity at flowering and filling stage ($P<0.01$).

Discussion

Soil enzyme activity is commonly regarded as the parameters for evaluating soil quality and soil biological activity (Liu et al., 2017), and plays an important role in soil nutrient cycling and transformation (Xue et al., 2003; Lu et al., 2002; Shu et al., 2010). Temperature is an important environmental factor affecting soil enzyme activity (Kang et al., 1999). In this study, covering 5 mm aluminum foil film (W1) at night promoted urease activity, invertase activity and cellulase activity in rhizospheric soil and non-rhizospheric soil of paddy fields. However, covering 11 mm aluminum foil film (W2) at night inhibited invertase activity, protease activity and urease activity in rhizospheric soil and non-rhizospheric soil (Figure 2; 4. 6; 8). The reasons may be that: (1) within the appropriate temperature range, soil warming can enhance microbial reproduction and metabolism rate, and produce more enzymes to participate in the carbon and nitrogen cycle, to expand the enzyme pool and enhance enzyme activity. When the temperature was higher than the suitable temperature range for soil enzyme activity, enzyme activity decreased. (2) nighttime warming increased soil ammonium nitrogen content, which inhibited soil urease and invertase activities (Jiang et al., 2018). The effects of temperature increase on soil enzyme activities were different. There are differences in the effects of temperature increase on soil enzyme activities, which may be the result of the joint action of soil and other environmental factors (Guo et al., 2017).

Biochar can affect soil enzyme activity by changing soil physical and chemical properties, composition and richness of soil biocommunity. Biochar has complex effects on soil enzyme activity, mainly related to soil enzyme species (Han et al., 2021). Biochar can adsorb enzyme substrate and promote enzymatic reaction. Conversely, enzyme molecules can also be adsorbed by biochar to mask the binding site of enzymatic reactions and inhibit enzymatic reactions (Elzobair et al., 2016). In this study, it was found that biochar application could promote soil urease and cellulase activities, which were significantly increased under warming treatment (Figure 2; 4). The reason may be that, the combined effect of temperature increase and biochar improves the soil environment, increases soil organic matter and soil temperature, and enhances soil enzyme activity (Jiang et al., 2019). Increasing biochar application rate (17.5t/ha biochar, B2) could inhibit invertase and protease activities in paddy soil. The reason may be that, biochar has a porous structure, a large specific surface area, and strong adsorption capacity, which reduces the reaction substrate of soil enzyme activity, and thus inhibits the production of soil enzyme activity (Wang et al., 2017).

Silicate application significantly promoted the activities of urease, cellulase, invertase and protease in rhizospheric soil and non-rhizospheric soil. Application of steel slag powder (Si1) significantly increased the activities of urease and cellulase in non-rhizospheric soil and the activities of invertase and protease in rhizospheric soil. Application of mineral powder (Si2) significantly increased the activities of cellulase in rhizospheric soil and invertase and protease in non-rhizospheric soil (Figure 2; 4. 6; 8). The reason may be that, application of steel slag powder and mineral powder improved soil structure and aeration, moderate soil acidity, make pH neutral, improve soil microbial habitat, facilitate soil microbial activities, and improve soil enzyme activity (Shen et al., 2015).

In conclusion, this study suggests the treatment with W2B1Si0 is the optimal combination, that is, soil enzyme activities were inhibited in the treatment with W2B1Si0, implying that the decomposition of organic carbon and nitrogen in paddy soil will be likely decreased with applying biochar without silicate supply under climate warming. This study was just a simulated warming experiment with rice under field conditions, which is easily affected by precipitation, temperature and other environmental factors. Further researches are needed to explore the response of soil enzyme activity to climate change, biochar types, supply amount through continuous field and controlled experiments, and to provide experimental reference for regional green and low-carbon sustainable rice production.

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Fig. 1 Effects of different treatments on urease activity in rhizospheric soil (A) and non-rhizospheric soil (B) at rice main growth stages

Fig. 2 Range analysis of urease activity in rhizospheric soil (A) and non-rhizospheric soil (B) with different treatments during the whole growth period of rice

Fig. 3 Effects of different treatments on cellulase activity in rhizospheric soil (A) and non-rhizospheric soil (B) at rice main growth stages

Fig. 4 Range analysis of cellulase activity in rhizospheric soil (A) and non-rhizospheric soil (B) with different treatments during the whole growth period of rice

Fig. 5 Effects of different treatments on invertase activity in rhizospheric soil (A) and non-rhizospheric soil (B) at rice main growth stages

Fig. 6 Range analysis of invertase activity in rhizospheric soil (A) and non-rhizospheric soil (B) with different treatments during the whole growth period of rice

Fig. 7 Effects of different treatments on protease activity in rhizospheric soil (A) and non-rhizospheric soil (B) at rice main growth stages

Fig. 8 Range analysis of protease activity in rhizospheric soil (A) and non-rhizospheric soil (B) with different treatments during the whole growth period of rice

Table 1 Variance Analysis of urease activity in the paddy soil

Factors	Growth periods				
	Elongation	Booting	Flowering	Filling	
Rhizospheric soil	Nighttime warming (W)	5.708*	0.615	1.857	2.217
	Biochar addition (B)	0.631	8.669*	0.156	1.479
	Silicate addition (Si)	0.378	0.078	1.477	0.328
Non-rhizospheric soil	Nighttime warming (W)	12.521**	1.346	14.347**	8.754*
	Biochar addition (B)	0.383	2.005	0.296	0.209
	Silicate addition (Si)	0.259	0.738	0.082	0.270

Note: * indicates $P < 0.05$; ** indicates $P < 0.01$. The same below.

Table 2 Variance Analysis of cellulase activity in the paddy soil

Factors	Growth periods				
	Elongation	Booting	Flowering	Filling	
Rhizospheric soil	Nighttime warming (W)	1.621	1.594	0.055	0.987
	Biochar addition (B)	1.438	0.015	1.347	0.113
	Silicate addition (Si)	1.094	1.535	0.802	0.669
Non-rhizospheric soil	Nighttime warming (W)	0.035	0.642	1.078	2.587
	Biochar addition (B)	0.222	2.798	1.821	0.088
	Silicate addition (Si)	19.352**	0.954	0.858	1.869

Table 3 Variance Analysis of invertase activity in the paddy soil

Factors	Growth periods				
	Elongation	Booting	Flowering	Filling	
Rhizospheric soil	Nighttime warming (W)	0.968	17.626**	0.323	0.193
	Biochar addition (B)	1.510	0.288	0.008	33.764**
	Silicate addition (Si)	1.380	0.155	8.683*	0.021
Non-rhizospheric soil	Nighttime warming (W)	0.877	0.177	0.835	0.561
	Biochar addition (B)	0.837	1.284	0.284	0.208
	Silicate addition (Si)	0.270	0.784	2.099	0.073

Table 4 Variance Analysis of protease activity in the paddy soil

Factors	Growth periods				
	Elongation	Booting	Flowering	Filling	
Rhizospheric soil	Nighttime warming (W)	0.384	0.116	2.076	0.054
	Biochar addition (B)	6.421*	47.342**	3.084	44.115**
	Silicate addition (Si)	0.134	0.027	0.192	0.019
	Nighttime warming (W)	0.580	0.280	0.010	0.130
Non-rhizospheric soil	Biochar addition (B)	2.338	3.095	8.238*	8.708*
	Silicate addition (Si)	0.781	0.367	0.542	0.248

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